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THE DYNAMICS OF PROCESSING SYNTACTIC UNITS IN UKRAINIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES

Modern teaching of Ukrainian as a foreign language aims to provide foreign students with grammatical knowledge and develop their skills for active use of the language in real-life communication situations. An important aspect of teaching is mastering syntactic units, as they are the foundation of speech activity and determine the structure of utterances. The dynamics of working on syntactic units in the classroom influence the effectiveness of students' acquisition of grammatical rules and their ability to construct correct sentences.

Syntactic units, as components of sentences, play a key role in teaching foreign languages, including Ukrainian as a foreign language. They can be classified as simple and complex sentences and their components, such as word combinations and phrases. The use of syntactic structures in the learning process is crucial for the development of communicative competence.

The Ukrainian language has specific features, such as word order in a sentence, the use of case forms, and various grammatical relations between sentence elements. These features pose challenges for foreign students, as they often struggle to construct correct sentences.

As Z. Matsiuk emphasizes, "...syntax plays a key role in the process of learning a foreign language. Parts of speech function in forms that are necessary to reflect relationships between objects, properties, and actions, and, in combination with lexical material, form sentences according to a specific pattern or model. Based on such a linguistic understanding of the hierarchy of language units, the principle of learning vocabulary and morphology based on syntax is established..." [6].

Psycholinguistic research confirms the concept of the predicative nature of internal language, which, in turn, justifies the structured organization of educational material on a syntactic basis. A description of functional syntax, which serves as the foundation for teaching Ukrainian syntax as a foreign language, can be found in the works of I. Vykhovanets [1], A. Zahnitko [3], M. Stepanenko [7], T. Masytska [5], M. Shleneva [8; 9] and other researchers.

The functional organization of grammatical material is implemented in textbooks by N. Zaichenko [4] and A. Demianiuk [2]. In these textbooks, syntactic structures are organized according to the expression of semantic relations, such as spatial, temporal, causal, purpose, condition, reason, and others. Using lexical and grammatical structures is intended to achieve communicative intent.

Teaching syntactic units involves the use of various methods, each with its pros and cons. Traditional methods, particularly the grammar-translation method, rely on exercises and memorization, which help students master the basics of grammar but do not always promote the active use of speech skills.

On the other hand, interactive methods, such as role-playing games, dialogues, group tasks, and simulations, stimulate student participation and create opportunities for applying syntactic structures in real-life situations. These methods help reinforce grammatical rules while simultaneously developing communication skills.

Contextual learning is an effective approach that incorporates texts and real-life examples to practice syntactic structures. This approach allows students to gain a deeper understanding of sentence structures and their functional meanings. Students can analyze texts to determine how different syntactic units convey meaning.

The dynamics of learning syntactic units also depend on various factors. The linguistic features of students' native languages can significantly influence the learning process, as word order and grammatical structures often differ between languages. For example, English has a more flexible word order, which can make constructing sentences in Ukrainian more challenging.

Psycholinguistic factors, such as motivation, cognitive abilities, and individual learning styles, also play a crucial role in learning syntax. High motivation and active participation accelerate the learning process. Pedagogical factors, such as the qualifications of teachers and the integration of modern teaching methods, including multimedia resources and interactive tasks, greatly enhance the effectiveness of the learning process.

To ensure that students fully master syntactic structures, it is essential to integrate traditional and modern teaching methods. Incorporating real-world situations and tasks that require students to apply new syntactic structures is a critical element of the learning process. The inclusion of multimedia resources, such as video and audio, enhances the understanding and retention of syntactic units.

Thus, the dynamics of working with syntactic units is a crucial aspect of teaching Ukrainian as a foreign language. A combination of varied teaching methods, interactive exercises, and a contextual approach fosters a deeper understanding of grammar, develops speech skills, and improves students' communicative competence.

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